

Title: Reply to Trinquart and Stockler's comments on clinical trial data sharing.

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Abstract:

Trinquart and Stockler propose the provision of stripped-down datasets for published clinical trials as an important step toward strengthening the willingness to share comprehensive data in clinical trials. However, the degree to which these approaches advance genuine data-sharing readiness warrants careful consideration since much inferential structure is lost when complex trial information is reduced.

To whom it my concern —

We read with interest the commentary by Trinquart and Stockler [1] on advancing clinical trial data sharing. We agree that, despite widespread support for transparency principles, access to individual participant data (IPD) remains slow, heterogeneous, and administratively demanding. Reducing these barriers is essential if data sharing is to fully deliver on reproducibility and cumulative learning in oncology [2].

Trinquart and Stockler propose the routine release of original stripped-down (time-to-event) datasets, motivated in part by advances in reverse data engineering [3], as pragmatic entry points toward greater readiness for data sharing. This suggestion acknowledges real constraints faced by many investigators and may lower the threshold for reproducibility or exploratory analyses, methodological research, and training. In such limited contexts, reconstructed data and stripped-down datasets can play a constructive role.

However, the degree to which these approaches advance *genuine* data-sharing readiness warrants careful consideration. Published trial reports are necessarily condensed representations of complex studies. Aggregate summaries and graphical displays do not retain key elements required for robust reanalysis, including censoring mechanisms (independent vs informative, administrative vs dropout-driven, assessment-schedule-dependent), covariate definitions, protocol deviations, and analytic flexibility. A stripped-down dataset is a deliberately simplified version of a full research dataset in which many variables, details, and contextual elements have been removed before sharing. Consequently, stripped-down or reconstructed datasets are inherently assumption-dependent and support only a narrow range of inferential questions. Different underlying data settings can yield identical stripped-down summaries, limiting their usefulness for assessing bias, missing data mechanisms, or alternative analytic strategies (identical stripped survival data \neq identical estimands).

This limitation is particularly relevant for oncology endpoints that embed layered clinical definitions. Distinct clinical progression criteria, assessment schedules, or handling of intercurrent events may produce the same marginal time-to-event summaries once reduced to a single outcome variable. Without detailed, machine-readable metadata that explicitly encode derivation logic and estimand choices, reconstructed data cannot preserve these semantic distinctions. While Trinquart and Stockler [1] also highlight the limited analytical value of stripped-down datasets, these constraints nonetheless illustrate how much inferential structure is lost when complex trial information are reduced.

For these reasons, reconstructed stripped-down datasets are best viewed as complementary tools rather than preparatory substitutes for IPD access. As the authors themselves caution, framing them as a “first step” risks obscuring the difference between analytical convenience and evidentiary adequacy and may shift substantial analytic effort to secondary users without strengthening transparency or accountability. Critically, as the authors do not claim otherwise, reverse engineering does not, by itself, build the governance frameworks, standardized metadata, data dictionaries, consent clarity, and analytic provenance that determine data-sharing readiness.

We therefore suggest explicitly positioning reverse data engineering or stripped-down datasets as a stopgap, exploratory approach, while prioritizing efforts to improve the efficiency and proportionality of data access mechanisms. Streamlined data-use agreements, tiered access models, and clearer journal expectations for IPD availability [2] are more likely to foster sustainable and trustworthy data sharing in oncology.

- [1] Trinquart L, Stockler MR (2025) The Paradox of Data Sharing in Cancer Randomized Clinical Trials - A Call for Greater Transparency. *JAMA Oncol*, 11(9):957-958.
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